

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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no3**

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Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities no3

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Disclaimer

RAMONES is a European Innovation Council (EIC) FET Proactive project in the Environmental Intelligence Scope B, related to radically novel approaches to resilient, reliable and environmentally responsible in-situ monitoring, funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 FET proactive programme, via grant agreement No. 101017808.

RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
GA	Google Analytics
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
SoA	State of the Art
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modeling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth and human health. RAMONES will provide tools for long-term, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, propose new AI-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these can be achieved by combining SoA equipment from various disciplines in well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. Additionally, one of the main goals is to introduce novel ways of monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political stakeholders at regular intervals from medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies.

The present document is the third installment of the dissemination and communication activities report, introducing the third year's progress towards the dissemination activities of our project. The report builds upon the activities and achievements that took place during M25-M36 of the project. The scope of the deliverable is to present an overview of the results achieved concerning the visual identity, the promotional tools, the publications and the templates produced in alignment with the project's objectives. More specifically the deliverable includes the following activities and tools:

- web related activities in digital channels
- material and templates regarding Communication activities
- articles and publications
- scientific events and activities organized and participated
- Environmental-, Radioactivity-, and Robotics-domain oriented activities
- established KPIs

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- dissemination activities

All of the above are being used to maximize the impact and raise awareness. as well as principally promote the RAMONES project in the overall scope of WP5.

1. WP5 / Dissemination & Communication Tasks

1.1 WP Objectives related to Dissemination and Communication

The objectives of WP5 which are relevant to the Citizen Awareness, Dissemination and Communication Activities are: (i) to establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work; (ii) to maximise the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements; (iii) to engage stakeholders that can support sustainability of the project via both update and feedback provisioning and can further empower the vision around the scientific domain communities, and (iv) to provide essential information and knowledge on the RAMONES project to 3rd parties activating esp. in H2020 and Environmental Intelligence landscape.

The WP is organized into six (6) tasks, from which the four (4) most relevant to the dissemination and outreach activities are presented below (T5.3-5.6).

There has been extensive use of online dissemination since the beginning of the RAMONES project, which continued till the present day. The overall progress is summarized together with analytics, showing the use of both the website and the relevant social media channels to promote the vision of the RAMONES project and disseminate its results to a wider, multi-faceted audience.

2. Communication activities

2.1 Digital channels

2.1.1 RAMONES project website

The design and development of the RAMONES website (<https://ramones-project.eu/>) was presented in the deliverable “D5.23 Website, Social Media” on M1 and its final release with some additions was presented in the document “D5.15 Material for Awareness, Communication, Dissemination and Outreach no2”. In the present deliverable, more additions and renewals have been made in the website such as dissemination material, deliverables etc. while a dedicated home button “Story Map” has been created to link to a open up a story map created for the scope of the project comprising all the tests, new release of instrumentation, up-to-date material and the latest information about the testing sites to the website visitors. The story map will be updated frequently, as has already been the case with the full content of the project website. The following Figures show screenshots of the latest content added in the website.

Figure 1 The renewed RAMONES website, now featuring a “Story Map” button in the main home page.

NEWS Archives – RAMONES Project

NEWS

Season Greetings

20 December 2023

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RAMONES collaborates with SANTORY in the field

21 November 2023

The first close monitoring of the active submarine volcano Kolumbo, north of Santorini Island, was achieved! A total of three oceanographic cruises were performed as part of our sister research project SANTORY with main objective to deploy various innovative instruments near the seabed inside the underwater volcano Kolumbo. The active hydrothermal vent system of Kolumbo (vents at...

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Metrics

The project's website serves as a continually evolving resource, receiving monthly updates that include recent developments, upcoming events, new publications, and project outputs. This site is dedicated to broadcasting the project's efforts and achievements, targeting a wide online audience ranging from stakeholders to the general public and beyond. Following the Google Analytics (GA) service which monitors the traffic of the website, yearly activity (M25-M36) of the website has been estimated and is highlighted below.

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Figure 3 Website activity concerning users and page views. Google Analytics is used; due to GA service change (GA3->GA4) data are shown in two different plots, till and after 16 Apr 2023.

In Fig. 3, a summary of the monthly project’s activity between M25 and M36 and users’ interaction with the website are presented in plots accompanied by statistics.

Moreover, the following resulting figures reflect a continuous and transversal work carried out by all partners during the third year of the project. The users by session default channel group over time are considered that shows that Direct and Organic Search prevail.

Website activity statistics are routinely examined using the Google Analytics tool for periodic analysis. The information concerning the location of the visitors, the visitors per country, website sessions per country, as well as the new users and pageviews per month are presented in the following figures. The reports on the website plainly reveal that the RAMONES project has triggered the interest of visitors from all around the world, especially USA, Greece, France, UK, Spain, Portugal, Germany, Italy and China. See Figures 4-8 for more details on the RAMONES website metrics. Important outcomes of the recorded trends is that RAMONES have reached a world-wide audience through its website and a cumulative curve of the new users per month shows that new users are constantly increasing.

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Users by Session default channel group over time

Figure 4 Overview of the users by Session default channel group over time (only GA4 data are shown).

Users by Session default channel group

Figure 5 Overview of the Users by Session default channel group.

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Users by Country ID

COUNTRY	USERS
Greece	180
United States	109
France	55
United Kingdom	53
Spain	45
Portugal	31
China	24

Jan 1 - Dec 21, 2023

[View countries](#)

Figure 6 Main visitors to RAMONES website per country.

Country	↓ Users	New users	Engaged sessions
	662 100% of total	658 100% of total	426 100% of total
1 Greece	180	179	200
2 United States	109	107	22
3 France	55	55	38
4 United Kingdom	53	53	19
5 Spain	45	43	30
6 Portugal	31	30	29
7 China	24	24	10
8 Germany	20	20	9
9 Italy	14	14	9
10 Netherlands	10	8	5

Figure 7 Distribution of website visitors per country (only GA4 data are shown).

Figure 8 User activity trending over time (M25-M36).

2.1.2 Story Map

The Story Map created for the purposes of the project is a widespread effective tool for promoting and introducing the project to a broad audience through modern technologies. For that purpose an ESRI ArcGIS Story map has been implemented to present at a glance the ongoing highlights of the project through a user-friendly and interactive way. Specifically, through story maps, information can be communicated, as well as scientific data can be disseminated and visualized. In this context, narrative text, images, videos, 3D representations, embedded items, and additional multimedia content are combined and published in a web-based application. Furthermore, the easy-to-use, multi-functional storytelling technology enables users to interact with the content and learn the project's scope and activities. New context is frequently added to keep the users of the webpage up to date with the progress and results of RAMONES.

The Story Map was implemented online in September 2023 (M33) after offline development and testing. It can be accessed through the link:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/391f0b5a0cc846039f49c0b6ff89ccc5>

Figure 9 The welcome page of the new Story Map of the RAMONES project.

The Story Map is organized across eight main tabs including information of the objectives of the project, marine radioactivity, project testing sites, instrumentation, field testings and connection to RAMONES social media. Screenshots of the story map are depicted below.

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About Marine radioactivity Testing sites Milos site Instrumentation Testings Consortium Follow us

Marine radioactivity

Marine radioactivity sources are found in all the oceans of the earth

Radioactivity in the marine environment is present either naturally or as a result of human activities. Naturally-occurring radioactivity makes up the majority of all radioactivity in the oceans with the largest contributions coming from potassium-40 and uranium-238 and its daughter nuclei, present from the formation of the Earth. Radioactivity from human sources is released into the marine environment from a variety of sources. These include planned releases (e.g. Fukushima), nuclear weapon testing, nuclear reprocessing plants and unintentional releases from events, such as the Chernobyl accident.

About Marine radioactivity Testing sites Milos site Instrumentation Testings Consortium Follow us

Map of the project's testing sites in Greece and France.

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About Marine radioactivity Testing sites Milos site Instrumentation Testings Consortium Follow us

Milos site

As an island of volcanic origin in the Aegean Sea, Milos has an ongoing underwater hydrothermal activity

Milos island constitutes an onshore and offshore hydrothermal system. The numerous faults of the island have served as conduits for geothermal manifestations extending from the shore to depths of 500 m or more. The most intense shallow hydrothermal venting activity (0–15 m water depth) is located along the SE coastline at Paleochori Bay. Moreover, other near-shore environments in Milos exhibit hydrothermal activity mostly at central and eastern part of the island.

The first field campaign of RAMONES for testing and validating the instruments was held in Milos shallow water hydrothermal fields on 24 - 30 of March 2023. Different locations were selected for establishing background radiation levels (gas & sediment sampling) in a known active vent field area for correlating it with RAMONES instruments and determining if sensors are sensitive for a full-fledged deployment that is useful for monitoring of a natural system. Engineering tests and water measurements in a real environment were performed for two γ -Sniffers, SUGI, CHERI UV camera, and the control unit of Panthia Lab. Overall, the preliminary results suggest that the

About Marine radioactivity Testing sites Milos site Instrumentation Testings Consortium Follow us

"We don't make music but we listen to the sounds of underwater bubbling volcanic fluids"

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Figure 10 Screenshots of the Story Map showing the main part of the application featuring eight main tabs and part of the page's content.

The RAMONES story map has collected close to 5 visits per month over a four-month span in the project's third year. It's noteworthy that during this specific period, the story map achieved nearly 600 views, with over 5 peaks of high traffic observed according to the following figure. This level of engagement highlights significant user interest at particular intervals, highlighting occasions the story map resonated strongly with the audience.

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Figure 11 Usage Trends: RAMONES Storymap Engagement and Peak View Analysis (Aug-Dec 2023).

2.1.3 Social media channels

The RAMONES project has implemented a sophisticated social media strategy, utilizing five (5) social media channels - Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube - to maximize its online presence and audience engagement. This strategy aligns closely with the project's identity and goals. Moreover, the activity of the RAMONES social networks is periodically monitored and reviewed on a weekly basis.

Key Elements of RAMONES's Social Media Strategy

Platform Integration: The project's use of social media is intricately linked with its website, ensuring consistency in brand identity and message dissemination across all digital platforms.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Regular monitoring of social media activities is conducted to assess the effectiveness of each platform. This helps in optimizing strategies and enhancing audience engagement.

Content Generation and Engagement: RAMONES maintains an active and continuous presence on social media. Regular updates on project-related events, scientific news, and other developments are shared, fostering interaction with followers and stakeholders.

Target Audience: The project's social media strategy is designed to cater to a diverse audience, including stakeholders, professionals, the general public, and academia. Each channel targets specific groups to maximize reach and impact.

Impact and Reach: The strategic and consistent use of social media has resulted in significant outreach and engagement, as reflected in various performance metrics. The project's social media presence has broad appeal and strengthens its online visibility.

Through this strategic approach, RAMONES demonstrates the importance and effectiveness of a well-planned social media presence in project communication and stakeholder engagement. The project's success in utilizing digital platforms highlights its commitment to leveraging modern communication channels for maximum impact and reach.

Tracking and metrics

On Facebook, an average of 3 posts per month were published, during a 12-month period in the third year of the project (M25-M36) with overall good impression and interaction indices. The Facebook page impact during the third year of the project had a small decrease reaching 3,324 number of persons that had an impact with the page.

Figure 12 Summary of Facebook activity of the third year of the project (M25-M36).

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Statistics about the age and gender of the followers on Facebook draw interesting inferences from the audience originating mostly from European countries (Greece, Holland, Portugal, Italy, Belgium, France, Sweden, Switzerland, U.K) and the U.S.A. The Total number of followers is 517 and total 'likes' this year is 488 adding 27 new 'likes'.

Figure 13 An estimation of the Facebook followers per gender.

The metrics also concern the views of the Facebook page during the third year of the project.

Figure 14 Views of our Facebook page during the third year of the project.

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RAMONES EU
Δημοσιεύτηκε από Stevi Kazana · 6 Οκτωβρίου ·

👉 The RAMONES team had a great opportunity to work together in Lisbon to evaluate the glider's hardware and software. The RAMONES partners from IST (Portugal), NTUA (Greece), Evologics (Germany) and Ploatech (Spain) were involved in the work and experiments performed in IST-ID facilities in Lisbon (Doca dos Olivais) and later at the Castelo de Bode dam for a full week in September (14-22/09/23) to perform various tasks of the project. The team integrated the USBL-Modems to the... [Δείτε περισσότερα](#)

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👍❤️ 22 1 σχόλιο 7 κοινοποιήσεις

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 RAMONES EU
Δημοσιεύτηκε από Stevi Kazana · 25 Σεπτεμβρίου · 🌐

A 3D model of our aSPECT prototype spectrometer V4 6in for in situ monitoring of alpha radiation was created by our NKUA partner Ioannis Madesis. ☢️
👉 Use the mouse to zoom and rotate the 3D sketch.
[#sketchfab](#) [#aspect](#) [#spectrometer](#) [#radioactivity](#) [#monitoring](#) [#ramones_eu](#) [#prototype](#) [#environmentalintelligence](#) [#h2020](#)

SKETCHFAB.COM
A Spect-prototype-V4-6in - Download Free 3D model by ioannismadesis - Sketchfab

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 7

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Figure 15 Screenshots of the Facebook posts and reactions.

Concerning the Instagram account, a total of 28 posts have been published on our Instagram account since the beginning of the project that promote our scope, daily activities, goals and achievements. The Instagram community is expanding reaching a total of 85 followers. Finally, the Instagram impressions increased the third year compared to the second year of the project by 12.8%, with a total of 918 impressions.

Figure 16 Per month Instagram impression of the third year of the project (M25-M36).

Figure 17 Total views of our Instagram page per month.

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Figure 18 Screenshot of the Instagram page showing the latest posts and activity.

On Twitter, 309 posts have been published on a monthly average during M25-M36, meaning that 244 more posts added this third year of the project, a number that represents the work done during this period. The page has 87 active followers who participate, comment and retweet the news of RAMONES.

Following is the monthly Twitter analytics for the period M25-M36.

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Your posts earned **253 impressions** over this **31 day period**

Your posts earned **1.4K impressions** over this **28 day period**

Your posts earned **225 impressions** over this **31 day period**

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Your posts earned **445 impressions** over this 30 day period

Your posts earned **598 impressions** over this 31 day period

Your posts earned **642 impressions** over this 30 day period

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Your posts earned **350 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your posts earned **123 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your posts earned **55 impressions** over this **30 day** period

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Your posts earned **102 impressions** over this **31 day** period

Your posts earned **320 impressions** over this **30 day** period

Your posts earned **69 impressions** over this **20 day** period

Figure 19 Monthly Twitter/X analytics for the @ramones_eu account (01.01.2023-20.12.2023).

Between M25 and M36, 4,682 new tweet impressions have been registered, reaching a total of 31,243 impressions overall, thus reaching 312% of the initially targeted 10,000 social media impressions for the full lifecycle of the project. The figure below shows the monthly evolution.

M25-M36 total impressions

Figure 20 RAMONES monthly (M25-M36) twitter/X impressions.

The analysis of the number of impressions to RAMONES twitter profile is an indication of how the project triggers interest, as well as the extent to which it is becoming known. The impact is closely linked to relevant events (such as the field tests of the RAMONES instruments), participation in events and congresses, other fairs and exhibitions.

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Figure 21 Screenshot of the RAMONES twitter profile showing recent activity and users interaction

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Due to the global coronavirus pandemic, all face-to-face activities had been severely restricted in M01-M24. To overcome this limitation, all the digital channels of the project have been strengthened and online activity has been strongly reinforced. As normality has slowly started to settle down in 2023 (M25 and on), in-presence dissemination channels (conferences, seminars, lectures etc) have strengthened gaining ground with respect to strictly digital channels, which continued to be used by the consortium.

On LinkedIn, a total of 17 new posts (total 47) were published during the (M25-M36) period receiving 294 new likes (total 644). The total views have been raised by 7686 new impressions and the followers until today are 157 (+59 since M24). See LinkedIn post impressions (Fig. 22), visitor engagement (Fig. 23) and samples of 2 posts on LinkedIn (Figs. 24 and 25).

Figure 22 Post impressions for LinkedIn in M25-M36.

Figure 23 Visitor engagement with RAMONES LinkedIn posts in M25-M36.

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Figure 24 Sample LinkedIn post #1.

Figure 25 Sample LinkedIn post #2.

On YouTube, 10 new videos have been posted in the period M25-M36, raising the total number of public videos in the RAMONES youtube channel to 13, see a sample screenshot in Fig. 26. With the new additions to the channel an aggregate number of 400 views has been recorded (+348 since M24). A total of 16 subscribers (+6 in M25-M36) have been recorded. The following pictures show the metrics of YouTube, such as total subscribers/views (Fig. 27) and total impressions (Fig. 28).

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Figure 26 A sample extract of a public video available on the RAMONES youtube channel (URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ryf_B1LMJxY).

Figure 27 Subscribers and total views of the YouTube channel for M25-M36.

Figure 28 Impressions of YouTube for M25-M36.

Finally, in the second year of the project again X/Twitter and Facebook are the main social media platforms that gather the most followers and impressions. LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube follow the other platforms, but still attract public attention and show rising trends.

2.1.4 Mailing & Newsletter activities

The RAMONES mailing list is a collection of email addresses of people that have subscribed to our newsletter through the project website or through the social media channels and story map. The mailing list is used for formal and official communication and is always open for new subscriptions to be added. This third year of the project, more people have subscribed to our newsletter in order to stay updated with the findings of the project, milestones and also to be informed about events, publications, synergies etc. relative to radioactivity monitoring and environmental intelligence fields.

Newsletters

As in the two first years of the projects, and in alignment with the initial committed biannual rate, two (2) newsletters have been published during the third year of the project (at M30 and M36). The newsletters comprise four articles each, which have been published in the RAMONES blog and are considered to have more suitable topics to the interests of the general public. The newsletters offer additional links to the full content of the website and social media channels.

The aims of the newsletters are:

- Informing project partners and stakeholders on the key findings of the project;
- Presenting the achievements, milestones, news scientific information of RAMONES;
- Disseminating participation in events, workshops and webinars organization, and more other relevant activities.

The following are indicative images that illustrate parts of the released 5th and 6th newsletters. At the point of authoring this report, the number of subscribers has reached 523.

Season Greetings

[Read more →](#)

RAMONES collaborates with SANTORY in the field

The first close monitoring of the active submarine volcano Kolumbo, north of Santorini Island, was achieved!

A total of three oceanographic cruises were performed as part of our sister research project **SANTORY** with main objective to deploy various innovative instruments near the seabed inside the underwater volcano Kolumbo.

[Read more →](#)

RAMONES Story Map

Our own Pavlos Kressakis and Stevi Kazana have created a **RAMONES StoryMap** where a concise and informational overview of RAMONES is combined with our recent progress on instrumentation and results. The **RAMONES StoryMap** is open to all, so feel free to distribute it to your networks via the link and QR code provided below.

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RAMONES participates to HNPS2023

It was a great pleasure and a good opportunity for RAMONES to present our recent progress of the instruments under development and test at the 31st Symposium of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society ([HNPS2023](#)). The Annual Symposium of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society is an international event that attracts researchers in Nuclear Physics and its applications. This year, [HNPS2023](#) was held at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) on Friday the 29th and Saturday the 30th of September, 2023. The Symposium presented state-of-the-art research activities on Theoretical and Experimental Nuclear Physics, Nuclear Astrophysics, as well as, Applications of the Nuclear Science including Nuclear Analytical Techniques, Nuclear Technology and Radiation Protection, Environmental Radioactivity and Bio-Medical Applications.

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Figure 29 RAMONES 6th Newsletter (M36; extract).

3. Dissemination activities

3.1 Publishing activities (Articles and publications)

Articles of general interest may be distributed over the press, other media sites or the web site of the project. Articles and publication production includes general purpose articles, press and media content, and scientific publications. The primary language is English, in order to reach the widest potential audience. However, the languages spoken in the project have been used according to the specific scope, publishing in other languages too. The website is the natural place to host all the work generated.

3.1.1 Articles of general and scientific purpose

The articles of scientific interest are 6 journal papers (Peer reviewed) and 2 conference papers (Peer reviewed):

Books

1. Reza Ghabcheloo and Antonio Pascoal, Editors, Motion Optimization and Control of Single and Multiple Autonomous Aerial, Land, and Marine Robots, Printed Edition of the Special Issue Published in Sensors, April 2023. ISBN 978-3-0365-6328-2 (hardback); ISBN 978-3-0365-6329-9(PDF). <https://doi.org/10.3390/books978-3-0365-6329-9>

Journal Papers (Peer reviewed)

1. V. Lagaki et al., JINST 18, T05001 (2023); doi: 10.1088/1748-0221/18/05/T05001
2. Pedro Mendes, Pedro Batista, Paulo Oliveira, and Carlos Silvestre, "Cooperative decentralized navigation algorithms based on bearing measurements for arbitrary measurement topologies," Ocean Engineering, vol. 270, 113564, February 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2022.113564>
3. Jiqiang Li, Guoqing Zhang, Antonio Pascoal, David Cabecinhas, "Prescribed performance path following control of USVs via an output based threshold rule," IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology (early access), December 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2023.3338518>
4. N. Hung, F. Rego, J. Quintas, J. Cruz, M. Jacinto, D. Souto, A. Potes, L. Sebastião, A. Pascoal, "A review of path following control strategies for autonomous robotic

vehicles: theory, simulations, and experiments,” *Journal of Field Robotics*, Vol. 40, Issue 3, May 2023, pp. 747-779. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rob.22142>

Conference Papers (peer reviewed)

1. G. Siltzovalis et al., *HNPS Adv. Nucl. Phys.* 29, 131 (2023), doi: 10.12681/hnpsanp.5096.
2. B. Psomas, I. Kakogeorgiou, K. Karantzalos, Y. Avrithis, “Keep It SimPool: Who Said Supervised Transformers Suffer from Attention Deficit?”. *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 5350-5360, 2023.
3. M. Chatsikian, V. Ntouskos, A. Mallios, K. Karantzalos, "Neural-based reconstruction of radioactivity distribution in large water volumes with underwater gliders", *10th Italian Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (AIRO)*, 2023.

Conference contributions (no proceedings)

1. P. Batista, D. Cabecinhas, L. Sebastião, A. Pascoal, T. Mertzimekis, K. Kebkal, A. Mallios, K. Karantzalos, K. Nikolopoulou, J. Escartín, L. Maigne, “The EU project RAMONES – continuous, long-term autonomous monitoring of underwater radioactivity,” *Atas 7.as Jornadas de Engenharia Hidrográfica / 2.as Jornadas Luso-Espanholas de Hidrografia*, pp. 351-354, Lisboa, Portugal, June 2022.

Master’s Thesis

1. V. Pedro, “*Optimal Path Planning for Radiation Detection with Autonomous Underwater Gliders*”, Master’s Thesis, Instituto Superior Técnico, 2024
2. D. Akanji, “*Cooperative Motion Control and Navigation of Autonomous Marine Vehicles for Ocean Observation*”, Master’s Thesis, Instituto Superior Técnico, 2024

3.2 Invited talks and lectures

The invited lectures listed below include topics that were inspired by and cover many of the topics addressed in the scope of the RAMONES project:

3. K. Nikolopoulos, “*Environmental Intelligence: the way forward*”, Seminar at Université Clermont Auvergne, 26.05.2023, organized by RAMONES partner Prof. L. Maigne
4. T.J. Mertzimekis, “*The RAMONES project*”, Seminar at Université Clermont Auvergne, 30.06.2023, organized by RAMONES partner Prof. L. Maigne

5. T.J. Mertzimekis, “*Nuclear Physics Applications: lessons from the past, challenges for the future*”, Athens People’s University, 14.12.2023 (in greek)
6. A. Pascoal, “Single and Cooperative Marine Robotics: an Introduction”, a three-day course offered at the Univ. Toulon, in the scope of the MIR Erasmus Mundus MSC Program, Toulon, France, March 2023.
7. A. Pascoal, “Exploring the Blue Frontier with Cooperative Marine Robots”, KAUST Research Conference on Robotics and Autonomy 2023, May 08 - 10, Saudi Arabia, 2023
8. A. Pascoal, “Ocean Technology Systems for Science, Industry, and Society,” invited lecture, Ocean Technology Systems for Science, Industry, and Society Session, Ciência 2023, 5-7 July, Aveiro, Portugal, 2023.
9. A. Pascoal, “Marine Robotics: from Technology to Science and Ocean Literacy”, BITS-PILANI, Goa, India, April 3, 2023.
10. A. Pascoal, “Exploring the Blue Frontier with Cooperative Marine Robots,” Plenary Lecture, The 13th National Technical Seminar on Unmanned System Technology 2023 (NUSYS’23), 2nd October 2023, USM Nibong Tebal, Malaysia

Event organization

Organization of the Marine Robotics School, Nov. 20-25, 2023, Goa, India.

<https://mrs2023.nio.res.in/>

General Program Chairs: Pramod Maurya, CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography (NIO), Goa, India; Jorge Dias, Institute of Systems and Robotics (ISR)/Univ. Coimbra, Portugal; António Pascoal, Laboratory for Robotics and Engineering Systems - ISR/IST Univ. Lisbon, Portugal

The school covered a large spectrum of disciplines and topics that are key to the design, implementation, and operation of single and multiple vehicles for commercial and scientific applications, with due account for the enabling technologies for multimodal communication networks. As a key distinctive feature, the participants were given a well-balanced presentation of theoretical and practical issues pertaining to marine robotic systems design. The conceptual aspects were firmly rooted in dynamical systems theory and optimization, machine learning and artificial intelligence in a marine robotics context, and techniques for navigation, guidance, and control of single and cooperative marine robots. The course also covered the steps required to go from concept to practice, by focusing on the process of systems implementation using the Robot Operating System (ROS) and Hardware-in-the-loop

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Simulations (HIL). Participants were invited to participate in demonstrations with marine vehicles and supporting systems provided by NIO and selected commercial companies. The school also featured a series of lectures and demonstrations with real equipment devoted to Networked Acoustic Systems, with applications to multiple vehicle communications and single/cooperative navigation and control.

Figure 30 The Marine Robotics School event in India.

3.3 Meetings

The RAMONES team held many meetings, almost exclusively by teleconference during this reporting period (M25-M36). Several meetings were held with relevant stakeholders and policy makers (e.g. with board members of the Hellenic Nuclear Physics Society or CNRS Executive Officers), presenting RAMONES and discussing innovation, business and the challenges of new technology and services to keep up-to-date and enrich the knowledge about the scope of the project, being the RAMONES digital channels, a fruitful point of contact.

3.4 Scientific events

The RAMONES team (co)organised workshops and attended several conferences, listed below.

Table 1 Scientific Workshops and conferences (co)organized or participated by RAMONES.

Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
Workshop #1 at UCA together with K. Nikolopoulos (UDUR)	Workshop	organization (UCA)	U. Clermont Auvergne, 26/5/2023

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Event Name	Type of event	RAMONES role	Place & Date
EMRA 2023	EU Workshop	presentation (IST-ID)	20-21/6/2023
iWoRiD 2023	International Workshop	Presentation (NTUA – poster)	Oslo, Norway, 25-29/6/2023
Workshop #2 at UCA together with T.J. Mertzimekis (NKUA)	Workshop	organization (UCA)	U. Clermont Auvergne, 30/6/2023
SEGH2023	International Conference	presentation (2 oral + 1 poster)	2-6/7/2023
ENVIRA2023	International Conference	presentation (1 oral + 1 poster)	17-22/9/2023
HNPS2023	International Symposium	presentation (2 oral + 1 poster)	29-30/9/2023
NTUA European Researchers's Night	Science Dissemination	Participation (NTUA)	29/9/2023
Ocean Business 2023	Exhibition and training forum	Attendee (PLOATECH)	Southampton, 18-20/4/2023
Erasmus Mundus Joint Master in Intelligent Field Robotic Systems	Lecture	Presentation (1 oral)	University of Girona, 24/4/2023

Figure 31 A picture from the Workshop #1 at Clermont.

4. Summary

As a conclusion, the following table summarizes the indicators of success of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. The details are presented in the Report of Activities section above.

1. KPI's concerning user (supply and demand) attraction up to the 36th month of the project (completion of the third year):

Table 2 KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized.	6	11	183%
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panelists on project specific topics.	14	17	114%

2. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

Table 3 KPIs concerning scientific dissemination.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Average technical blog posts per year	2	2	100%
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	10	22	220%
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artifacts	12	18	150%
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	50	29	58%
Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	3	0	0
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	8	7	88%
Ecosystem	Percentage of Open Access publications	>70%	90%	100%
Wide range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	3	12	367%
Wide range	Commercial exploitation events participation	5	5	100%

3. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

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Table 4 KPIs concerning social dissemination.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Wide range	Websites launched (workplan)	1	1	100%
Wide range	Website content updating (average)	monthly	monthly	100%
Ecosystem	Templates for dissemination activities and other material	2	2	100%
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per year	6	6	100%
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	3	8	267%
Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4	5	125%
Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	10000	37912	379%
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	1200	862	72%
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	2	4.5	225%
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	4	3	75%
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	8	5	62%
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	8	6	75%

4. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Table 5 KPIs concerning strengthening impact via joint efforts.

Range	Type of dissemination and communication activities	Target	Contributed values	Accomplished
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & other projects liaised with RAMONES	6	17	283%
Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties.	5	5	100%
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	2	0	0
Ecosystem	3rd party datathons/hackathons supported by project	2	0	0
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	200	0	0

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Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	1800	16216	901%
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